

Exploring non-education faculty's lived teaching experiences in a Philippine higher education institution

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative, phenomenological study investigates the impact of lacking formal pedagogical training on non-education faculty in the context of Caraga State University Cabadbaran Campus (CSUCC). The research explores their lived experiences to understand the specific challenges and coping mechanisms they employ in their teaching roles. Data was collected through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with a purposive sample of ten non-education faculty members representing various disciplines at CSUCC. The sample size of 10 participants was determined by the principle of data saturation, ensuring the collection of rich and recurring data to identify significant themes. Several key themes emerged through thematic analysis of the transcribed interviews and focus group discussions. These included self-perceived teaching efficacy, difficulties encountered in test construction and syllabus design, challenges related to student engagement, and the utilization of available resources and support systems. The findings of this study provide valuable practical implications for higher education institutions (HEIs). They suggest the necessity of implementing targeted training programs, offering relevant professional development opportunities, and establishing dedicated resources to support non-education faculty better. Ultimately, these interventions aim to enhance teaching quality, improve faculty satisfaction, and foster a more supportive teaching and learning environment.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Entering the field of education with unrealistic expectations about teaching can lead to negative experiences for new educators. Faculty members play a significant role in determining the success of students' learning outcomes [1]. One existing issue, especially in higher education, is "out-of-field" teaching, where faculty members teach subjects outside their major field of specialization, potentially affecting instructional quality and learner engagement. Producing quality faculty members requires improving the quality of teaching they can deliver [2]. Educators, at all levels, are vital in shaping learners' academic and personal growth by promoting knowledge, instilling positive attitudes, and revealing their unique potential.

The widespread of non-education faculty in educational settings has rapidly increased, bringing diverse skills, and expertise. However, a major issue in the teaching and learning process is the need for more pedagogical training for these faculty. Several studies indicated that there are a number of faculty teaching

outside their field of specialization, even though they hold the essential qualifications [3]. This situation is particularly prevalent in the Philippines, especially in higher education institutions (HEIs). There are also instances where faculty teach in their major field but without formal pedagogical training, and some are new to the teaching profession. Given the significant role of faculty members in students' academic journeys, it is vital that newly recruited faculty apply the appropriate teaching practices to meet learners' needs [4].

Non-education faculty often encounter a crucial transition from their original profession to teaching. This transition provides challenges, highlighting the need for appropriate support programs. Gaining pedagogical knowledge and skills is critical for these educators. Previous studies underscore the value of professional development programs in improving teaching abilities among those with non-traditional educational backgrounds [5]. Effective teaching methods depend on the faculty's discretion in setting objectives, developing lessons, selecting materials, and implementing assessment strategies.

Previous study by Avendaño *et al.* [6] reported the positive effect of pedagogical training on other professionals transitioning to teaching, improving their teaching competencies through specialized training focused on pedagogical knowledge, practice, and the improvement of pedagogical skills. Faculty without formal education backgrounds often experience more significant challenges in their teaching careers than those with education degrees [7]. While they are bringing important job-related skills like interpersonal abilities and communication, they may lack pedagogical skills and instructional leadership. It is essential to create a supportive learning environment where these faculty members can demonstrate their impact to motivate learners.

An educator's main responsibility is to establish meaningful learning environments that encourage learners to achieve their full potential [8], empowering them to become self-motivated, lifelong learners [9]. However, non-education faculty experience different challenges, from lesson planning and managing classrooms to assessing learner progress [10]. These challenges underscore the demand to balance content knowledge with pedagogical skills, particularly in higher education, where effective teaching directly affects learner success. The fast advancement of technology and the shift toward flexible learning environments further require adaptability and innovation from faculty members.

The widespread presence of non-education faculty in HEIs is a prevalent phenomenon in the Philippines. Many faculty members specialized in fields outside education with limited formal training in teaching are presently employed in various colleges and universities. While existing literature underscores the significance of pedagogical training and support, there is a lack of study specifically investigating the lived experiences of non-education faculty in the Philippines.

This study fills this critical gap by exploring the social meanings, challenges, and adaptive strategies utilized by non-education faculty teaching in HEIs through the lens of Caraga State University Cabadbaran Campus (CSUCC). The novelty of this study lies in its extensive exploration of the lived teaching experiences of non-education faculty in Philippine HEIs, particularly at CSUCC. Unlike past studies that generally look into faculty development or pedagogical challenges in wider contexts, this study offers a more focused phenomenological inquiry into how non-education faculty handles the complexities of teaching without formal pedagogical training. By recognizing critical themes such as self-perceived teaching efficacy, test construction and syllabus design difficulties, learner engagement challenges, and resource allocation limitations, the study provides a refined understanding of the adaptive strategies used by these faculty members. A very important contribution of this study is its application of situated learning theory to describe how non-education faculty improved teaching competencies through actual practice, peer mentorship and collaboration, and institutional support instead of traditional pedagogical training.

In addition, it underscores the unusual struggles faced in discipline-specific teaching, strengthening the need for specific professional development programs. The study's findings have significant implications for HEIs, highlighting the need for structured mentorship programs, support systems, and resource allocation to address pedagogical problems. This study, therefore, fills a critical gap in the previous studies by giving empirical evidence on the challenges and coping mechanisms of non-education faculty, offering realistic recommendations to enhance teaching quality and faculty development programs in similar institutional settings.

2. COMPREHENSIVE THEORETICAL BASIS

This study is tied with the theory developed by Lave and Wenger [11], situated learning theory. The concept of situated learning theory explains that unintentional learning construction happens within the framework of genuine practices, specific environments, and cultural norms. In addition, Lave and Wenger [11] claimed that learning is embedded within an authentic activity, context, and cultural background, often happening incidentally. Furthermore, beginner learners, also known as novices, should engage in authentic

settings of daily practices, applying knowledge, and utilizing artefacts in productive yet low-risk manners [12]. This theory further explains the importance of delivering learning experiences realistically and authentically.

In addition, situated learning theory discusses that learning occurs best when it takes place in the context in which it is applied. An individual should act in an apprentice capacity within communities of practice where learning opportunities arise situationally. Situated learning theory posits that engagement with individuals from varied opportunity profiles leads to one's opportunities and fosters personal, professional, and intellectual development. Moreover, when teachers are novices, they can benefit from the expertise of experienced professionals within the practical environment in the working space. Therefore, experienced teachers can be a great source of strength for sharing beneficial and constructive suggestions that help develop self-efficacy and self-confidence among novice teachers in their teaching practices [13].

Furthermore, it is explained that beginning professionals do not only accumulate professional skills by collecting facts. However, it is facilitated through community social interaction through collaborative activities with professionals. Social interaction and collaboration within a community are crucial for learning. Working with and learning from experienced professionals is critical to growth.

The situated learning theory in Figure 1 emphasizes the importance of social interaction and context in the learning process. The illustration shows how learning occurs through interaction. Novices on the periphery of the community of practice learn by observing and interacting with experts in the center. As novices become more proficient, they move closer to the community's center and eventually become experts. Lave and Wenger [11] asserted that learning is not simply acquiring knowledge but rather a process of becoming a part of a community of practice. Through constant involvement in activities, the use of artefacts, the development of identities, and the formation of relationships within a community of practice, beginners learn the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to become experts. Moreover, Lave and Wenger [11] explained that the community of practice model is important in understanding how learning happens in the real world. It can be applied to different settings, such as workplaces, schools, and online communities.

Figure 1. Lave and Wenger [11] situated the learning theory model

3. METHOD

3.1. Research design

This study used a qualitative, phenomenological approach, which gathers data through interviews and focus group discussions. This research approach focuses on understanding non-education faculty lived experiences and the intrinsic nature of these experiences. The phenomenological approach explores how individuals perceive and understand their world [14]. Unlike other approaches aiming to uncover objective truths, phenomenology appreciates the subjective, personal meaning an individual attaches to experiences, underscoring the essential part or core nature of a shared phenomenon, such as grief, learning, or experiences.

3.2. Data collection and analysis

For data collection, the researchers utilized in-depth interviews and focus group discussions employing a semi-structured interview questionnaire with open-ended questions. This would allow the participants to describe their teaching experiences in their own words. The questionnaire was validated by research experts before the actual data gathering. Observations and assessments of teaching performance were also used to gather rich qualitative and descriptive data. Researchers coded and categorized responses to identify central themes for data analysis. They employed thematic analysis and hermeneutic interpretation techniques to reveal more profound insights into a systematic organization of patterns within faculty experiences and a deeper, contextually grounded interpretation of their meanings.

The thematic analysis identifies and structure's key themes, while hermeneutic interpretation ensures that these themes are understood in their full depth, considering personal, institutional, and cultural factors. This dual approach strengthens the research's validity and contributes to a richer understanding of non-education faculty's teaching experiences, ultimately offering meaningful recommendations for professional development and institutional support. A critical part of these approaches is the researcher's role in bracketing or setting aside personal biases, a process known as *epoché*, to genuinely engage with participants' perspectives [15]. The researchers interpreted experiences faithfully by prioritizing participants' unique insights while uncovering universal elements across individual accounts.

3.3. Research participants

The 65 identified non-education graduate faculty are currently employed at CSUCC. Out of the total number of 65, the researchers identified 10 as sample participants for the conduct of interviews and focus discussions. While there are no hard and fast rules around how many people should be involved in qualitative research, some researchers estimate that between 10 and 50 participants will be sufficient depending on the type of research and research question [16]. These 10 sample participants were identified using the principle of data saturation, ensuring the collection of rich and recurring data to identify significant themes. Purposive sampling was also applied, which uses particular criteria that participants must meet during selection. In most cases, purposive sampling is recommended since focus group discussions and interviews depend on participants' ability and capacity to provide relevant information [17]. These 10 participants came from the four colleges and one department of this campus, namely the College of Industrial Technology and Teacher Education (CITTE), with two participants, the College of Tourism and Hospitality Management (CTHM) with two participants, College of Engineering and Information Technology (CEIT) with two participants, College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) also with two participants, and another two participants from the General Education Department (GenEd).

3.4. Limitations

This study is not without its limitations due to its sole focus on the CSUCC. Such a narrow sample size and institution context limit the scope of generalizability. Besides, self-selection and social desirability biases might creep in due to participant responses. Other limitations of the study include its snapshot in time and methodological restrictions that result from data collection mechanisms and sample size. To minimize these limitations, the researchers considered triangulation, rigorous sampling, reflexivity, a strong theoretical framework, and contextualization in their analysis and interpretation of the results. Triangulation was done by gathering data from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, classroom observations, and teaching performance evaluation results from the college deans.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Throughout the interview process, several critical themes appeared. These are self-perceived teaching efficacy, test construction and syllabus preparation issues, student engagement difficulties, and availability of resources and support systems to address teaching challenges. Some of these critical themes contain diverse sub-themes that add depth to the understanding of teachers' experiences. These sub-themes were explored in detail and compared with findings from existing literature and related studies to highlight areas of agreement or contrast. This is to provide a comprehensive perspective of the complexities faced by non-education faculty in teaching. Practical implications are also provided and explained for future action to ensure a fair and high-quality education for all.

4.1. Self-perceived teaching efficacy

During the interviews and focus group discussions, a number of critical themes emerged related to self-perceived teaching efficacy among faculty without formal training in education. A notable theme was the

need for formal educational training, as many non-education faculties expressed difficulties in performing an important teaching practice, like lesson planning. One participant said:

“He has not gone through formal education training, so he does not have enough knowledge about lesson planning.”

This issue suggests that faculty without formal training may lack the structured approach offered by pedagogical content knowledge, which aids educators in delivering course content systematically and caters to diverse learning styles [18]. As a result, learners with diverse learning needs may not receive enough support, potentially affecting their learning experience.

Interestingly, while formally trained faculty often adhere to established instructional methodology, faculty without such training likely rely on personal instinct and versatility. One participant shared, *“while he was teaching, he did not follow a formal method,”* revealing a versatile yet potentially inconsistent strategy. Although this versatility allows faculty members to respond to classroom dynamics instantaneously, it may limit the consistency and structure some learners need to optimize learning outcomes. This finding highlights the balance between theoretical knowledge and practical experience in terms of teaching effectiveness. Many participants in this study preferred hands-on application over theory, often relying on their industrial experience to fill in the formal training gaps, as indicated by the response of one participant who said, *“her background is in company work, so she is more exposed to practical applications.”* While this industry experience may help in developing real-world skills, it may also lead to spontaneous “on-the-spot” teaching, which could compromise the need for a strong theoretical foundation which is critical for a comprehensive learning environment [19].

Moreover, selecting appropriate learning resources emerged as a critical challenge. Some faculty members need formal training to align instructional materials with curriculum objectives. One participant mentioned that she gets confused about which specific reference to use because there are so many, depending on the subject, emphasizing confusion due to insufficient knowledge about instructional guides. This problem is further amplified by limited access to updated instructional materials, specifically by the non-education faculty. The inability to identify or create appropriate teaching resources may lead to a decrease in instructional quality, creating disparities in learners’ educational experiences [20]. The findings entail the need for additional support and structured mentorship to help non-education faculty address these issues and ensure a more coherent and inclusive learning environment.

The findings’ implications are critical for educational institutions, educators without proper training, and learners. For educational institutions, this requires targeted professional development, mentorship activities, enhanced resource accessibility, and re-assessment of recruitment practices to reduce the potential negative effect on student learning outcomes. For untrained educators, the lack of pedagogical content knowledge hinders effective lesson planning and delivery, leading to reliance on intuition, which creates inconsistency. They also struggle with resource selection and require structured support to bridge these gaps, as practical experience alone cannot replace theoretical grounding. Lastly, learners face the potential risk of erratic learning experiences and unfulfilled learning needs due to variations in faculty preparedness, emphasizing the significance of institutional action to ensure fair and high-quality education for all.

4.2. Test construction and syllabus-making challenges

Another crucial theme that emerged during interviews was the non-education faculty’s difficulties in making syllabi, tables of specification (TOS), and questionnaires for examination. Critical concerns include the lack of training and guidance, with participants revealing they needed to be trained in syllabus development and how to align assessment. For example, one participant stated that he was never taught how to do it emphasizing the need for professional training. Non-education faculty often rely on revising existing syllabi and TOS without proper guidance rather than creating their own content, as evidenced by another participant who shared that she borrowed an old syllabus, and then read all the contents and modified what she thought was necessary to revise. This practice highlighted its dependence on pre-existing frameworks and revealed a need for more work to innovate effectively, hindering the potential for a more customized instructional and assessment design.

These challenges reveal a tension between compliance and instructional flexibility, with educators sometimes prioritizing effective teaching over strict adherence to standardized syllabi. While institutional requirements demand consistency, educators desire flexibility as they balance syllabus requirements with practical teaching methods. This finding contradicts Chen [21] who assert that syllabus content must be extremely similar to institutional requirements to consistently align with program standards. The consequences are that more adaptable and consistent syllabus templates are required that provide a foundation but may not accommodate varying teaching methods.

The sub-theme related to content delivery and pedagogy reflects a shift towards prioritizing understanding and application over simple memorization. Teachers are increasingly engaging students through the application of higher-order thinking skills (HOTS). This shift acknowledges the need to foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills in order to prepare students to adapt to a constantly changing global environment. According to previous studies [22], [23], modern education standards highlight the importance of competencies in terms of college and career readiness, reflecting that teaching methods and assessment strategies must evolve to meet these new demands. This further implies that faculty development programs should focus on methodologies that can trigger deeper learning, thus preparing students more effectively for complex, real-world problems.

The value of a TOS together with the syllabi further highlights the need for consistency in the methods of assessment. Practical realities like class disruption and time constraints, however, prevent the consistent use of TOS frameworks, that tend to require adjustments like make-up classes to allow for effective curriculum delivery. This aspect highlights the need for institutional support and flexible timetables to enable good and high-quality assessment practices.

Finally, faculty members without pedagogical training have unique difficulties in assessing the understanding of students. For example, one participant stated:

“Ang ako gyud, kay dili man gyud ko educ. Dili kayo nako ma-determine if understanding ba siya, application ba siya, evaluation ba siya.”

“Since I do not have an education background. I cannot always determine if it is understanding, application, or evaluation.” (Translation)

Thus, it highlighting the challenge in differentiating the levels of cognitive assessment. This is a strong indication that faculty members lacking pedagogical education might not be able to accurately measure the understanding and application competencies of students, thus hindering themselves from effectively gauging learning accomplishments.

The results have serious implications for the development of faculty training programs, where experiential education is highlighted as being necessary in the mentioned areas. Specifically, the training programs need to focus on syllabus design, assessment alignment, and application of new pedagogical strategies to increase instructional quality and student performance. Addressing these weaknesses will enable faculty members to effectively guide learning experiences and adapt to the ever-evolving nature of modern education.

4.3. Student engagement challenges

A major topic in this study was student involvement issues, which underlined the need for non-educational faculty members to use different approaches to improve student involvement, particularly those who cannot directly relate to the topic. Improving teaching strategies to foster a more inclusive, efficient learning environment depends on these engagement techniques [24], [25]. Non-education faculty were seen in the classroom employing interactive and cooperative techniques to promote active learning and peer interaction. Emphasizing the importance of group discussion in knowledge development, one participant said:

“We have collective discussions to explore different ideas.”

This strategy fits with studies trying to connect positive results like enhanced knowledge retention and cognitive development to classroom-based engagement.

Another equally important factor is the faculty’s expertise. Participants revealed that industry experience brings significance to the classroom. It can connect lessons to real-world applications and future career opportunities. One participant confidently shared,

“Wala kayo koy problem kay ang akoang expertise... dali ra nila ma-adapt.”

“I do not have much of a problem since my expertise makes it easy for students to adapt.” (Translation)

This finding emphasizes the motivational effect of real-world insights. However, existing studies report that teaching skills may be more significant than industry experience alone, as some faculty with wide content knowledge may still lack the ability to effectively foster engagement [26]. This suggests that while industry experience is critical, the ability to develop a supportive, engaging learning condition is essential.

Strategies for assessment and feedback are also extremely important. Regular comments and various assessment techniques show the non-education faculty’s dedication to closing learning gaps and improving

teaching practices. One participant said, “*I want comments from my students to enhance my teaching strategies.*” stressing the need for student feedback for self-improvement is a reflection of a willingness to improve depending on student experience. Another participant said, “*I welcome negative feedback and let students express themselves.*” This strategy allows non-education faculty to handle particular areas requiring change, improves the teaching process, and promotes ongoing development. These results highlight the need for faculty development initiatives that equip educators with assessment techniques, instructional flexibility, and student involvement. These are also very critical for non-education faculty members to maximize their impact and create a good learning environment [27].

4.4. Resources and support systems to overcome teaching challenges

During interviews and focus group discussions, a number of key support systems that non-education faculty find extremely helpful in overcoming higher education teaching issues were identified. These are laboratory facilities, institutional support, professional development, peer advice, adaptation to technology, discipline-specific instruments, individual drive, and mentoring. Each area of support fulfils a different need and, in total, contributes to the effectiveness of teaching among non-education faculty.

4.4.1. Laboratory resources

Non-education faculty highlighted the necessity for well-equipped laboratories, particularly in scientific and technical fields. Laboratory resources facilitate experiential, hands-on learning in accordance with commission on higher education (CHED) standards, facilitating knowledge application by the faculty with practical skills. The study highlights that well-equipped laboratories increase student engagement and understanding through an immersing learning environment [28].

4.4.2. Institutional support

Assets like library resources and institutional funding are important in addressing teaching needs. The provision of complete and updated teaching materials to non-education faculty helps to ensure successful teaching and efficient content delivery [29]. Institutional support helps to fill pedagogical knowledge gaps and equip faculty with materials to achieve instructional objectives.

4.4.3. Professional development

Seminars and training provide non-education faculty with useful knowledge of the latest teaching methods and pedagogical practices, which is particularly important for those who do not have formal educational backgrounds. This ongoing professional development has resulted in enhanced instructional quality and pedagogy. In addition, this training has increased faculty confidence in being able to meet the variety of learning needs of their students [30].

4.4.4. Peer support

Support from colleagues and mentorship provide non-formal guidance, preventing isolation and facilitating instructional skill enhancement. Peer partnerships result in the presence of others, which has been reported as particularly helpful when promoting faculty development to enhance the teaching and learning process [31]. It allows people to share excellent teaching practices that can effectively support professional enhancement.

4.4.5. Adaptation to technology

Non-education faculty use technology like Google Classroom and PowerPoint to effectively organize and present the content of a particular subject. These technologies not only make the students more engaged but also simplify teaching and learning tasks. As a result, educators are able to effectively deliver lessons despite limited formal pedagogical training [32], [33].

4.4.6. Difficulties with discipline-specific tools

For certain disciplines, writing-oriented and application-based methods are more appropriate than conventional lecture styles. Non-education faculty needs to change their modes of instruction, which in many cases could be impossible without proper training. Studies underscore the advantages of discipline-specific teaching methods, noting the need for synchronizing the teaching approaches with subject demands [34].

4.4.7. Individual initiative

In times of limited resources, non-educational faculty often take the initiative to develop their own teaching materials. Such a proactive approach reflects the resourcefulness and adaptability of these teachers. Ultimately, this resourcefulness helps them meet instructional needs even under adverse limitations [35].

4.4.8. Mentorship and legacy

Mentorship by experienced peers is vital in helping novice teachers, especially those who do not have teaching degrees. With mentorship, non-education faculty are given guidance in addressing teaching difficulties, acquiring best practices, and strengthening classroom management skills. Such support greatly enhances both instructional quality and job satisfaction [36].

Figure 2 employs a puzzle piece analogy to illustrate the interconnected components essential for empowering non-education faculty in teaching. A graduation cap in the middle represents successful learning and teaching, with pieces around it representing key support factors: mentorship, lab facilities, institutional support (policies, funding, and administration), professional development, peer support, technology accommodation, discipline-specific tools, and individual initiative. The figure highlights that empowering these faculty needs a comprehensive strategy combining institutional support, professional development, teamwork, sufficient resources, technological competency, and individual motivation to successfully merge subject matter expertise with good pedagogy and ultimately enhance student learning [37].

Figure 2. Teaching support for non-education faculty

5. CONCLUSION

This research opens the door to the intricate balance between content area knowledge and instructional practice for faculty from non-education backgrounds stepping into teaching assignments. Although they contribute significant world experience and trade knowledge to their classrooms, not having received explicit pedagogical training creates dilemmas in the areas of planning lessons, course syllabi creation, and grading alignment. These challenges tend to result in the use of intuition and experience over formal educational frameworks, which may result in inconsistencies in student learning experiences. The study, however, points out the high commitment of these faculty members to teaching as they actively pursue and apply available resources, such as peer support, institutional programs, digital tools, and self-developed instructional materials to fill pedagogical gaps.

From the perspective of situated learning theory, these results emphasize the social and contextual nature of learning. Non-education faculty build teaching effectiveness through active involvement in real teaching contexts, casual mentorship, peer support, and professional development activities. Their stepwise engagement in academic communities of practice enables them to perfect pedagogical techniques and synchronize instructional approaches with educational best practices. The research illustrates that institutional support through facilities like laboratories, training seminars, and responsive digital resources is important to enable this situated learning process by offering chances for faculty to participate in effective practice-based learning experiences.

Further, discipline-specific challenges emphasize the importance of support systems that recognize the distinctive demands of different fields. Lecture-based models might not necessarily fit industry-oriented disciplines, so faculty's requirement to learn within their own teaching environments through practice and

collaboration becomes more important. Finally, the research results emphasize the importance of organized professional development, mentorship, and available resources to enable non-education faculty to combine their practical expertise with effective pedagogy, resulting in improved student learning outcomes. Future research may explore the long-term impact of situated learning-based training programs on teaching efficacy and identify ways institutions can optimize support structures to harness the strengths of non-education faculty across diverse academic settings.

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C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : Writing - **O**riginal Draft

E : Writing - Review & **E**ditng

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

There is no conflict of interest for this study.

INFORMED CONSENT

The authors obtained informed consent from all participants in this study.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The University currently does not have an institutional ethics board, but it has a Research, Innovation, and Extension Office, which serves as an equivalent committee for research approval. Research related to human use has been complied with all the relevant national regulations, including the data privacy law of the Philippines and institutional policies in accordance with the tenets of the Helsinki Declaration and has been approved by the Office of Research, Innovation, and Extension (ORIE). The scholarly work for this research has undergone a rigorous review and evaluation by the experts from ORIE and has been approved by the University President through the recommendation of the Vice President for Research, Innovation, and Extension. The mechanism for approval ultimately aligns with journal guidelines for ethical oversight.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data supporting this study's findings are available on request from the corresponding author [JML]. The data, which contain information that could compromise the privacy of research participants, are not publicly available due to certain restrictions from the data privacy law of the Philippines.

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